

Research Article

Growth Performance of Broiler Birds Produced in Four Different Rearing Conditions

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Abstract

Growth performance was monitored on broilers produced in four different rearing conditions which consisted of cage having direct exposure to the sunlight, A, cage having partial exposure to the sun, B, cage having no exposure to the sun light as the cage was surrounded by leafy Moringa trees, C, and deep litter pen, D. Four hundred commercial broiler chicks of 30 days old were reared in the four different rearing conditions for a period of two weeks. Each of the rearing condition had one hundred 30 days old broiler chicks. Five broiler birds in each of the rearing conditions were randomly tagged for daily data recording in order to obtain body weight gain, feed conversion ratio and production efficiency factor at the end of the study. Feed and water were measured and given to ensure uniformity. All routine health schedules recommended for broiler birds in Nigeria were strictly adhered to. Test results revealed that cage C produced the best result which had the highest mean body weight gain and mean production efficiency factor of 838g and 289.56, respectively. It was also revealed that rearing condition at all levels had a significant effect at $P < 0.05$ on the three measured parameters considered in this study. It was recommended that rearing broiler birds in an outdoor elevated cage with leafy Moringa trees planted beside it should be encouraged in Nigeria for increased growth and production rate.

Key Words: Broiler, rearing conditions, performance evaluation

Received: 22/04/18

Accepted: 28/07/18

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Introduction

The rapid increases in population, urbanization, and standard of living in many developing countries, including Nigeria, have resulted in higher demand for animal protein. The poultry industry has played a prominent role in attempts to meet this increased demand. Poultry meat is one of the most consumed animal protein, unrestricted by any religion or culture in Nigeria. Broiler meat, according to Omodele and Okere (2014), constitutes about 15.2% of total poultry meat consumption in Nigeria and this figure is projected to increase.

Among the different rearing systems for broiler production, a majority of broiler farmers in Nigeria engage in deep litter system for rearing, using battery cages for layers due to the initial cost of the cage or its sophistication (Lamidi, 2005). Many farmers believe that conventional confinement systems lead to animal stress, resulting in negative physiological responses and poor growth. According to Mikulski *et al.* (2011), outdoor rearing systems could improve bird growth and reduce stress. Environment-controlled housing has made the maximum expression of genetic potential possible in broilers (Kao *et al.*, 2011) as harsh environmental conditions have a negative impact on the health and performance of poultry (Dawkins *et al.*, 2004; Estevez, 2007).

The welfare of a bird, is a difficult concept to define and even more difficult to access. Nevertheless a variety of indicators including health, productivity, behavioural and psychological characteristics are commonly used to reveal this situation (Cunningham and Mauldin, 1996). Performance of a bird can therefore be gauged by the overall welfare in relation to its environment.

In recent years, the increased emphasis on regulation has driven changes on how animals are fed and managed and will continue, possibly in an accelerated manner with much pressure on reducing costs to increase supply through the use of larger and more integrated facilities (McWilliams, 1993) in a sustainable production system. Gordon and Charles (2011) observed a multitude of factors such as genotype, age, sex, diet, density, environment and exercise, impact growth performance of birds.

The broiler rearing system is a crucial factor affecting birds comfort, health and production efficiency (Fouad *et al.*, 2008). In recent years, a lot of research is being conducted on the alternate rearing systems instead of floor (Zimmerman *et al.*, 2006). However, Swain *et al.* (2002) reported that rearing system (deep litter versus cage) had no significant effect on feed intake and feed conversion ratio (FCR) of broilers (Santos *et al.*, 2012). As a way to provide an alternative rearing system on broiler

production, the need to conduct this study became very imperative. The objective of this study was to determine how some rearing systems under different conditions affect the efficiency and performance of broiler birds in Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out at the Integrated Farm Unit of the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria in February 2016. A total of 400 broilers of 30 days old were used for this study. After brooding that took 30 days, 100 broilers were transferred evenly to the different rearing systems under different conditions and were fed with commercial broiler finisher for 14 days. Three elevated outdoor cages A, B and C having a dimension of 3m wide, 5m long and 1.5m high together with a deep litter pen, D, of 3 m wide and 5 m long were used for this study. Cage A had direct exposure to the sun, cage B had partial exposure to the sun and cage C had no exposure to the sun as it was surrounded by Moringa trees. A, B, C and D as described forms the four different rearing conditions used for this study.

Five broiler birds were chosen at random from each of the rearing conditions at the start of the experiment and marked by the side for the purpose of identifying the broiler birds that will be constantly used for measurement in the four different rearing conditions adopted for the study. Each of the selected broiler was weighed at the onset of the experiment which is the 31st day. The broilers were fed with commercial broiler finisher feed (Top feed; made in Nigeria by Premier Feed Mills, Co. Ltd) three times daily (8a.m., 1p.m. and 4p.m. at 50%, 20% and 30% of their daily ration, respectively) for the 14 days duration of the experiment. The broiler birds were fed 100 g per broiler bird per day in the first 5 days of the experiment, 120 g for the next 7 days of the experiment and 140 g for the last 2 days of the experiment. Adequate hygiene was maintained around the farm. The broiler birds were vaccinated with ND and IBD oral vaccine in order to prevent them against the prevailing avian diseases in Nigeria and were given the same antibiotic and anticoccidial therapy. The feed was measured to ensure all treatments (rearing conditions) had same ration throughout the duration of the experiment. An electronic scale with model number: EK5350, made in China was used for weighing the broiler birds' daily weight.

Data collection

Daily record was taken for feed, water intake and body weight gain of all the marked broiler birds in each of the rearing condition. The body weight gain (BWG),

feed conversion ratio (FCR) and production efficiency factor (PEF) was calculated using the following formulas:

Body Weight Gain

The body weight gain by the broiler bird was determined as:

$$BWG = W_f - W_i \quad (1)$$

where,

BWG = Body weight gain by the broiler bird (g)

W_f = Final weight of the sample broiler bird (g)

W_i = Initial weight of the sample broiler bird (g)

Feed Conversion Ratio

The feed conversion ratio (FCR) was determined as:

$$FCR = \frac{\text{Body weight gain}}{\text{Amount of feed used to gain that body weight}} \quad (2)$$

where,

FCR = Feed conversion ratio

Production Efficiency Factor

The production efficiency factor (PEF) was determined as:

$$PEF = \frac{\text{Average daily body weight gain} \times \% \text{ survival}}{FCR \times 10} \quad (3)$$

where,

PEF = Production efficiency factor

FCR = Feed conversion ratio

Statistical Analysis

The completely randomized design (CRD) was adopted for this study. The data obtained were statistically analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) technique and the means were compared using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). The SPSS statistical analysis software package version 20.0 was used for data computation.

Results and Discussion

Tables 1 to 3 present the results obtained for the measured parameters during the period of study. Tables 4 to 6 presents the ANOVA results obtained for the measured parameters. Results shown in Tables 4 to 6 showed that the rearing condition at all levels had a significant effect at $P < 0.05$ on all the measured parameters. Table 7 presents the result of Duncan's Multiple Range Test obtained for the mean difference of the measured parameters considered in this study.

Table 1. Body Weight Gain by the Broiler Birds during the period of Study

Broiler bird S/No.	Rearing Condition			
	A	B	C	D
1	705	723	832	818
2	654	684	820	724
3	730	782	814	802
4	694	675	833	764
5	623	640	891	790
Mean	681.2	700.8	838	779.6

Key: A = Cage with direct exposure to the sun; B = Cage with partial exposure to the sun; C = Cage with no exposure to the sun as it was surrounded by Moringa trees; D = Deep litter pen.

Table 2. Feed Conversion Ratio for the Broiler Birds fed during the period of Study

Broiler bird S/No.	Rearing Condition			
	A	B	C	D
1	2.30	2.24	1.95	1.98
2	2.48	2.34	1.98	2.24
3	2.22	2.07	1.99	2.02
4	2.33	2.40	1.94	2.12
5	2.60	2.53	1.82	2.05
Mean	2.39	2.32	1.94	2.08

Key: A = Cage with direct exposure to the sun; B = Cage with partial exposure to the sun; C = Cage with no exposure to the sun as it was surrounded by Moringa trees; D = Deep litter pen.

Table 3. Production Efficiency Factor of the Broiler birds during the period of Study

Broiler Bird S/No.	Rearing Condition			
	A	B	C	D
1	218.94	228.24	298.67	277.39
2	188.36	206.70	289.90	217.02
3	234.88	267.14	286.33	266.58
4	212.75	198.88	300.57	241.97
5	171.15	178.88	342.69	258.75
Mean	205.22	215.97	303.63	252.34

Note: Survival rate obtained for broiler birds reared in A, B, C and D were 100%, 99%, 98% and 94%, respectively.

Key: A = Cage with direct exposure to the sun; B = Cage with partial exposure to the sun; C = Cage with no exposure to the sun as it was surrounded by Moringa trees; D = Deep litter pen.

Table 4. ANOVA result for Body Weight Gain

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	78871.000	3	26290.333	14.938	0.000067
Within Groups	28158.800	16	1759.925		
Total	107029.800	19			

Table 5. ANOVA result for Feed Conversion Ratio

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	.650	3	.217	12.722	0.000166
Within Groups	.273	16	.017		
Total	.923	19			

Table 6. ANOVA result for Production Efficiency Factor

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	29576.104	3	9858.701	13.878	0.000102
Within Groups	11366.129	16	710.383		
Total	40942.233	19			

Table 7. Mean Difference between Measured Parameters

Cage	BWG	FCR	PEF
A	681.20 ^a	2.39 ^b	205.22 ^a
B	700.80 ^a	2.32 ^b	215.97 ^a
C	838.00 ^c	1.94 ^a	303.63 ^c
Deep Litters	779.60 ^b	2.08 ^a	252.34 ^b

Means with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different from each other at (P<0.05)

Keynote: A = Cage with direct exposure to the sun; B = Cage with partial exposure to the sun; C = Cage with no exposure to the sun as it was surrounded by Moringa trees; D = Deep litter pen; BWG = Body weight gain; FCR = Feed conversion ratio; PEF= Production efficiency factor

Body Weight Gain

The body weight gain (BWG) by the broiler birds as presented in the ANOVA result shown in Table 4 showed they were affected by the different rearing conditions used for rearing the broiler birds. From Table 7, it can be deduced that cage C had the highest mean body weight gain value of 838.0 g. The deep litterpen had the next highest mean value of 779.60g. Mean body weight gain values obtained for broiler birds reared in cages A and B showed no significant difference at P<0.05 as their mean values were statistically the same. This indicates that the natural shed housing system is suitable for rearing of poultry birds in order to achieve a substantial body weight gain.

Feed Conversion Ratio

The feed conversion ratio (FCR) of the broiler birds as presented in the ANOVA result shown in Table 5 showed they were affected by the different rearing conditions used for rearing the broiler birds. The feed conversion ratios obtained for the broiler birds in cages A and B as shown in Table 7 were statistically different from

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 ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

broiler birds reared in cage C and deep litterpen. Cage A had the highest mean feed conversion ratio of 2.39 which was immediately followed by cage B that had a mean feed conversion ratio of 2.32. There was no significant difference at $p < 0.05$ observed between the feed conversion ratios obtained for cages A and B. Likewise, there was no significant difference at $p < 0.05$ observed between the mean feed conversion ratios obtained for cage C and deep litter pen. This result revealed that low-light stimulated the feed conversion ratio of the broiler birds as broiler birds fully and partially exposed to sunlight tend to convert a lower proportion of feed to meat than broiler birds in the shade (cage C) and in the deep litter pen rearing conditions.

Production Efficiency Factor

The production efficiency factor (PEF) of the broiler birds as presented in the ANOVA result shown in Table 6 showed they were affected by the different rearing conditions used for rearing the broiler birds. Table 6 also revealed that there is a proportional relationship that exists between the body weight gain of the broiler birds and their production efficiency factor. The broiler birds in cage C had the highest production efficiency factor of 303.63 than the broiler birds reared in cages A and B. This was immediately followed by a deep litter pen with a production efficiency factor of 252.34. Production efficiency factor obtained for broiler birds in cages A and B showed their mean values were statistically the same, while production efficiency factor obtained for cage C and deep litter pen were statistically different from one another. This result implies that exposure of broiler birds to sunlight reduced their production efficiency factor.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it was generally observed from the results obtained that apart from the genetic factors, the different rearing conditions used for rearing the broiler birds in the study are also a function of their performance. It was deduced also that though direct exposure to sunlight may influence feeding rate and water intake which in turn attributed to the high feed conversion ratio, it may also affect production efficiency factor as indicated by the values obtained from the statistical result.

Recommendation

From the outcome of this study, it is recommended that broiler bird farmers in Nigeria should adopt outdoor elevated cages with trees planted beside it for better market weight gain per floor area per broiler bird because of higher body weight gain of the broiler birds and consequent high economic return of this system.

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